

IMPACT OF THICK CFRP PANELS: A PARAMETRIC STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic laminates of the order of 24mm thick are being considered for the wing panels of large civil aircraft. The behaviour of such panels under low velocity impact has not yet been considered in detail. In this paper results are presented from a parametric study into the effect, on impact performance, of panel thickness and unsupported diameter. The panel thickness was varied from 4mm to 24mm and the unsupported diameter from 200mm to 1m. This work was carried out using axi-symmetric finite element models with ABAQUS. The impact was modelled as equivalent to dropping a tool with a mass of 1kg from a position 4m above the panel, directly onto its centre, giving an impact energy of 40J. The ABAQUS/Explicit solver was used to create detailed time-history results in every case. The panel was modelled with isotropic properties in plane with a reduced stiffness through the thickness. The simulations were purely linear elastic with no failure criterion or damping.

It was found that the axial and shear stresses were small. The radial and hoop stresses were significant and were examined in more detail. The maximum radial and hoop stresses on the bottom surface were found to be biggest for panels with the smallest diameter and thickness. Also it was found that for the thicker panels, the radial and hoop stresses were largely independent of panel diameter. In fact the stress history results showed that they were either very similar or identical during the first 0.5ms of the impact, during which the maximum stresses were attained. Both maximum deflection and impact event duration were bigger for panels with a larger diameter and a smaller thickness.

It was observed that in most of the cases studied the contact between impactor and panel was not continuous during the impact event, but a series of up to five distinct periods of contact. It was also found that the maximum displacement of the panel generally occurred when the panel and impactor were not in contact and was due not to the direct influence of the impactor, but its indirect influence in setting up multiple modes of vibration in the panel.

These simulations have demonstrated the effect of panel geometry on stress and deflection during an impact event. More importantly, the simulations suggest that under certain conditions the impact response of a large panel may be determined from a test on a smaller laboratory specimen.

KEY TERMS: Impact response, thick laminates, explicit FEA, parametric investigation, stress

INTRODUCTION

There is currently a desire to use composite laminates throughout the structure of large civil aircraft. In particular, use of composites for wing skins is being investigated where thicknesses up to 24mm are common. Such wing skins are vulnerable to damage from dropped tools during maintenance and other such accidental impacts. The resulting damage can be invisible from the surface and also leads to conservative design.

There has been extensive research into modelling an impact event on a composite laminate, using a variety of approaches. Some researchers have developed closed form solutions, though these have limited applicability and are often not as accessible as approaches based on computational methods, such as the finite element (FE) method. Some researchers have chosen to use existing, commercially available, FE codes. When modelling panel impact, researchers have variously used 3D ([2], [4], [6] – [8]), 2D shell ([1], [10]), and stacked 2D shell ([3], [5]) FE models. Usually the lay-up is modelled either explicitly with a layer of elements for each ply, or by using a composite element that smears the ply properties across the thickness of the element sometimes with integration points at each ply interface.

Often the focus of the research is to model damage evolution. This has been achieved in a number of ways, using damage mechanics, or a series of stress based failure criteria, where element properties are updated with deteriorated values when the criteria is met [4]. Some researchers, instead of updating element properties, updated the strain energy [2] or stress [7] in the relevant elements. Damage propagation is commonly predicted with fracture mechanics [5], treating delaminations as cracks. When the aim is to model the effect that damage has on the response of the panel, the model is often less complicated. The target laminate can be approximated to a spring and mass system [9] providing no detailed prediction of the stress state of the laminate is required. A standard shell element model can be adapted to include the effect of damage simply by inclusion of a gap and a dashpot element [10], which can model the panel response provided accurate values for the dashpot and gap element parameters can be found.

Most of this research has made the assumption that the low velocity impact being simulated is essentially a quasi-static event and hence use implicit solvers. This may be the case but use of this type of solver means that detailed time history results of the panel response is harder to obtain, and some of the high frequency transient effects are missed. In this paper ABAQUS/Explicit is used; the manner in which it computes a solution means that the transient response of the panel is captured in detail.

Most research so far into impact has been on thin laminates, typically no thicker than 2 or 3mm. Only a few recent papers were found that analysed or experimented on what might be considered a thick laminate [8], [11], [12]. Almost by definition experimental studies are conducted on coupons, not on full sized structures. Typically the unsupported diameter in a coupon study is 100-200mm, whereas the unsupported dimension in a real structure could be more than ten times that. To relate the response and damage found in experiment to that which might happen in a real structure is difficult. Hence the aim of this study is to investigate the relevance of coupon based tests to real structure response, in particular that of thick laminates: this research considers panel thicknesses in the range of 4mm to 24mm. A series of finite element models have been analysed in a parametric study of the influence of panel geometry to its impact response.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A total of 20 different finite element models were used in this study. This corresponds to a model for each thickness (4, 8, 12 and 24mm) and diameter (200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000mm) combination. All of the models share the same basic geometry and boundary conditions, presented below.

Before any detailed analysis was conducted a mesh convergence study was performed. It was found that using one element per mm thickness was sufficient to give converged results.

ABAQUS/CAE version 6.2 was used to create input decks for ABAQUS/Explicit version 6.2 to solve. The solutions were carried out on a Silicon Graphics Origin 200 server with a 133MHz processor and 128MB of RAM.

Ideally the impact of a flat panel would be carried out with a fully three-dimensional model that represents the exact geometry of the panel. However the analysis of such a model is very computationally expensive; hence all the models are axi-symmetric. This meant that special two-dimensional elements could be used, giving much lower solution run times. Use of an axi-symmetric model does limit the panel geometry to that of a circular plate; the material properties have to be axi-symmetric also, hence the exact ply by ply lay-up could not be modelled.

Figure 1 – Basic model geometry

Model Boundary Conditions

Figure 1 shows the basic model geometry. The impactor is modelled as an analytically rigid spherical body with a diameter of 25mm. All the impactor’s boundary and initial conditions are applied to its reference point at its centre. Table 1 shows the boundary and initial conditions that are used in every model.

Table 1 – Common model boundary and initial conditions

Initial impactor velocity	8.86m/s
Impactor mass	1.02kg
Drop height	4m
Impactor force due to gravity	10.0N
Impactor/panel contact	Hard, frictionless

The drop height chosen enables calculation of a consistent impact velocity, but the simulation starts from the instant the impactor makes contact with the panel. The panel is modelled as built-in around its circumference with an encasté condition applied to the appropriate edge in the model. The effect of gravity on the panel is assumed to be negligible and is not included. ABAQUS does not assume any symmetry conditions so these were applied to both impactor and panel along the axis of symmetry.

The panel was assumed to be isotropic in plane with a reduced stiffness through the thickness. The generic carbon fibre epoxy laminate material properties shown in Table 2 were used (1 and 3 are the in-plane axes, and 2 is the through-thickness axis), and applied using the engineering constants method in ABAQUS.

Table 2 – Finite element model panel material properties

$E_1 (= E_3)$ (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	$G_{12} (= G_{23})$ (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	ν_{13}	Density (kg/m ³)
56.24	9.655	4.552	21.37	0.316	1620

Finite Element Mesh

Figure 2 shows the main features of every mesh.

Figure 2 – Main features of every mesh

In every mesh there is a region of square elements under the impactor. The radius of this region and hence the size of the elements are exactly the same in every model. Five positions are examined in particular detail in every model. The deflection of the impactor and the panel at points A and B and the stress at the integration point of elements i and ii. In the remaining part of the model, the same number of elements are kept through the thickness, but their length in the radial direction gradually increases towards the outer edge of the panel. The average aspect ratio (length to height ratio) is always between two and three, and the worst aspect ratio is never more than six.

The element used in every mesh is a four noded, reduced integration, axi-symmetric element denoted CAX4R in ABAQUS. There are no quadratic elements available in the ABAQUS/Explicit code.

RESULTS

Each model produced detailed time-history results for every requested variable. Of particular interest was the displacement (calculated at the element nodes) of the impactor and the panel at points A and B (see Figure 2), and the stress (calculated at the integration point of every element) for elements i and ii. The displacements at points A and B were found to be very similar and hence where panel displacement is shown, this is for the centre of the panel. Figures 3 and 4 show typical results that ABAQUS produced for each model.

Figure 3 – Time history results for displacement for the 8mm thick, 1m diameter panel

Figure 4 – Time history results for hoop stress for the 8mm thick, 1m diameter panel

From graphs such as these various important pieces of data can be obtained. For example from Figure 3, the duration of the impact event and the maximum deflection of the impact event can be ascertained. From Figure 4 the maximum stress in the model can be found by simple observation. Interestingly Figure 3 shows that the impact event is not one continuous period of contact, but in fact a series of interruptions in contact. For example, at about 1.5ms after first contact the impactor and panel separate for a period of about 0.5ms.

It was observed that the radial and hoop stresses were significant in elements i and ii, whereas the through thickness and shear stresses were small in comparison and hence are not considered here. The radial and hoop stresses were also found to be very similar to each other in their time history and magnitude.

Using the important data garnered from each graph it is possible to build a picture of the effect that the geometrical parameters have on the impact response of a panel, in particular the maximum stress, maximum deflection and impact event duration. In Appendix A seven tables show the values of the parameters for every model. Figure 5 shows the variation of maximum stress with panel thickness for each panel diameter, Figure 6 that for impact event duration and Figure 7 that for maximum deflection.

Figure 5 – Maximum radial stress in every model

Figure 6 – Impact event duration in every model

Figure 7 – Maximum deflection at the centre of the panel in every model

DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows that the smaller panels in both diameter and thickness have higher maximum stresses. Due to their higher bending stiffness, thicker panels are less likely to experience deflection due to bending, but more shear deflection and indentation directly under the impactor. For these reasons the maximum stress on the bottom surface of the panel is likely to be lower in thicker panels.

A similar argument holds for panel diameter. Panels with a larger diameter are less stiff in bending and will therefore have a lower maximum stress on their lower surface. More importantly it shows that maximum stress becomes largely independent of panel diameter for thicker panels. This validates a coupon based investigation, at least in terms of maximum stress, when the panels are thick.

It was also found that the stress history, at least for models with the same thickness, was the same in the first few moments of the impact event, as illustrated in Figure 8. It shows the stress history for all five 12mm thick models. Only the 200mm and 400mm diameter models show significant deviation before 0.6ms. The remaining three models all exhibit the same maximum stress, and it occurs at the same moment (0.2ms).

Figure 6 shows that, for the most part, the panels with larger diameters and smaller thicknesses have longer impact event durations. These panels are generally less stiff and hence will not rebound the impactor (and end the impact event) as quickly. The results for the 1m diameter, 12mm thick panel does not fit this pattern. The reason for this is thought to be that the panel is oscillating wildly and hence loses contact with the panel sooner than might have been expected, thanks largely due to the interruptions in contact.

Figure 7 shows that the thinner and larger diameter panels have bigger maximum deflections. This is because these panels have lower stiffnesses and hence can deflect more from the impact. In addition, in a similar way to the maximum stress, there appears to be a convergence as the panels get thicker, where the maximum deflection becomes independent to the panel dimensions. Note this is the deflection at point B (see Figure 2) and hence any effect due to indenting under the impactor will be minimised.

Figure 8 – Hoop stress history for every 12mm thick model

CONCLUSIONS

A range of 20 different panel geometries has been analysed; the effect of panel diameter and thickness on the panels' response investigated. In particular the impact event duration, maximum stress and maximum deflection have been studied by scrutiny of time history results from ABAQUS/Explicit finite element models.

It was found that thinner and larger diameter panels have bigger maximum deflections, panels with larger diameters and smaller thicknesses have longer impact event durations and smaller panels in both diameter and thickness have higher maximum stresses.

In particular it was shown that the maximum stress becomes largely independent of panel diameter for thicker panels.

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APPENDIX

The following seven tables summarise the important results from the analyses.

Table A1 - Maximum radial stress in element i (MPa)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	1988	1759	1163	975	659
8	1010	804	516	368	367
12	631	453	310	310	310
24	215	169	169	169	169

Table A2 - Maximum radial stress in element ii (MPa)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	310	274	236	182	183
8	198	227	170	150	114
12	137	156	123	109	117
24	55	86	71	70	70

Table A3 - Maximum hoop stress in element i (MPa)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	1904	1687	1123	942	640
8	991	788	503	360	360
12	626	450	308	308	308
24	215	169	169	169	168

Table A4 - Maximum hoop stress in element ii (MPa)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	416	397	303	239	200
8	306	312	200	156	151
12	222	216	138	138	138
24	98	97	97	97	97

Table A5 – % of Impact Event in Contact (ms)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	100	100	100	85	64
8	100	100	79	52	32
12	100	100	73	43	70
24	100	100	100	100	100

Table A6 – Duration of impact event (ms)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	2.1	3.5	3.9	6.6	7.8
8	1.05	2	2.65	4.65	7.1
12	0.73	1	2	3.45	1.65
24	0.47	0.68	0.48	0.48	0.48

Table A7 – Maximum deflection at point B during impact event (mm)

	Plate Diameter (mm)				
Plate Thickness (mm)	200	400	600	800	1000
4	5.84	9.28	11.05	12.31	13.56
8	2.5	4.45	6.44	8.23	8.89
12	1.38	2.47	3.79	4.61	5.06
24	0.43	0.96	0.94	0.95	0.95